

INTERACTIONS OF MANGANESE AND NICKEL ATOM CLUSTERS IN THE SILICON LATTICE

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Annotation. This work presents a study of the interactions between clusters of manganese and nickel atoms within a silicon lattice. It has been established that as a result of these interactions, multicharged manganese nanoclusters and nickel atom clusters are destroyed, leading to significant changes in the magnetic and photoelectric properties of the samples. The obtained results are explained by the formation of electrically neutral complexes between nickel and manganese atoms (Ni--Mn^{++}) in the silicon lattice, i.e., the formation of binary clusters Ni--Mn^{++} .

Keywords. Manganese clusters; Atomic interactions ; Electronic properties; Crystal lattice modification; computational modeling; Impurity effects in silicon.

As shown in works [1,2], under certain thermodynamic conditions, nickel atoms in the silicon lattice form electrically neutral clusters ranging from several nanometers to several microns in size. Manganese atoms, in contrast, form clusters consisting of four neighboring atoms.

The interaction of impurity atom clusters of different nature presents considerable scientific and practical interest [3,4]. Firstly, such research makes it possible to reveal the characteristics of the interactions of impurity atom clusters, assess their stability and state within the lattice; secondly, to determine the potential for self-organization of binary clusters with various impurity atoms; and finally, to elucidate the mechanisms of self-organization and the kinetics of cluster formation. Controlling the composition, structure, and size of both monoatomic and binary impurity clusters in a crystal lattice of various nature allows one to determine the functional capabilities of such materials. As shown in [5], multicharged manganese nanoclusters are formed only in compensated samples, where manganese atoms are in the Mn^{++} state. The formation of nickel atom clusters in silicon does not depend on the type or concentration of the initial impurity atoms. Manganese was introduced by gas-phase diffusion, while nickel was introduced from a metallic layer applied to the silicon surface. Three batches of samples were prepared: the first batch for nickel atom diffusion only, the second for manganese atom diffusion only, and the third for simultaneous diffusion—nickel applied to one surface of the sample and manganese introduced via the gas phase. The samples were placed in individual evacuated quartz ampoules, and diffusion was conducted at temperatures ranging from 980°C to 1130°C in 30°C increments. The diffusion time was 60–90 minutes. After diffusion, the ampoules were cooled and subjected to identical technical and chemical treatments. The electrophysical parameters of the samples were measured using the Hall effect method. The results are shown in the table.

No.	Diffusion Temperature	Samples	ρ , $\text{Ohm}\cdot\text{cm}$	Type
	$T = 980^\circ\text{C}$	$\text{Si}\langle\text{B},\text{Mn}\rangle$	1.5×10^2	p
		$\text{Si}\langle\text{B},\text{Ni},\text{Mn}\rangle$	9.6	p
		$\text{Si}\langle\text{B},\text{Ni}\rangle$	9.3	p
	$T = 1010^\circ\text{C}$	$\text{Si}\langle\text{B},\text{Mn}\rangle$	4.5×10^2	p

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		Si<B,Ni,Mn>	9.8	p
		Si<B,Ni>	8.02	p
	T = 1040°C	Si<B,Mn>	6.5×10^3	p
		Si<B,Ni,Mn>	18.7	p
		Si<B,Ni>	7.93	p
	T = 1070°C	Si<B,Mn>	5.1×10^4	p
		Si<B,Ni,Mn>	1.07×10^2	p
		Si<B,Ni>	7.93	p
	T = 1100°C	Si<B,Mn>	2.7×10^3	n
		Si<B,Ni,Mn>	9.2×10^2	p
		Si<B,Ni>	7.9	p
	T = 1130°C	Si<B,Mn>	1.7×10^2	n
		Si<B,Ni,Mn>	6.2×10^3	p
		Si<B,Ni>	7.9	p

As seen, up to a diffusion temperature of $T = 1040^\circ\text{C}$, the manganese-doped samples remain p-type, but their resistivity increases from 10 to $6.5 \times 10^3 \text{ Ohm}\cdot\text{cm}$. At $T > 1080^\circ\text{C}$, the samples become n-type, and their resistivity decreases with further increases in temperature. These results show that manganese acts as a donor impurity in silicon, with the concentration of electrically active atoms changing from 3×10^{14} to $3.5 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ in the studied temperature range, consistent with [5].

Nickel-doped samples remain p-type throughout the temperature range, with only a slight decrease in resistivity as temperature increases, indicating that nickel acts as an acceptor impurity with a concentration of $N = (4-6) \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

Thus, in all studied temperature ranges, the concentration of electrically active manganese atoms is 8–10 times greater than that of nickel atoms. This leads to the conclusion that in samples doped with both elements, the material properties are primarily determined by manganese. However, as the table shows, samples doped with both Ni and Mn exhibit an interesting behavior. Up to $T = 1010^\circ\text{C}$, the Si<B,Ni,Mn> samples remain p-type, but their resistivity decreases. At $T = 1040^\circ\text{C}$, they return to their initial values ($\rho \sim 9-18 \text{ Ohm}\cdot\text{cm}$), as if no Ni or Mn atoms were present.

Above $T = 1070^\circ\text{C}$, resistivity increases but the conduction type remains p. This behavior cannot be explained by compensation of Mn donor levels by Ni acceptor levels, since at $T = 1040^\circ\text{C}$ the concentration of electrically active Mn atoms is ~ 15 times greater than Ni.

Nickel atoms at lattice sites act as acceptors with two levels, which are mostly unoccupied in p-type materials. Meanwhile, manganese atoms in interstitial sites act as double donors. Manganese atoms can donate their outer ($4S^2$) electrons to Ni atoms at lattice sites, forming neutral complexes. This formation prevents hole compensation and additional hole generation due to Ni energy levels (ionization energy $E_v + 0.2 \text{ eV}$). In this case, the samples should retain their initial properties, as confirmed experimentally.

To satisfy this, Ni atoms in the lattice must be twice as concentrated as electrically active Mn atoms in interstitial sites. Thus, neutral complex formation likely promotes Ni atoms occupying lattice sites. This explains the reduction in size and concentration of Ni clusters in such samples. The change in conductivity type of Si<B,Ni,Mn> at $T > 1070^\circ\text{C}$ can be attributed to the breakdown of these complexes and hole compensation by Mn electrons.

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This is supported by the fact that Si<B,Ni,Mn> samples which became n-type at $T = 1100^{\circ}\text{C}$ returned to p-type with original parameters ($\rho \sim 10 \text{ Ohm}\cdot\text{cm}$) after annealing at $T = 1040^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The presence of Ni atoms in interstitial sites hinders Mn cluster formation, explaining the formation of Ni--Mn⁺⁺ binary complexes, with Ni in lattice sites and Mn in interstitial sites.

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